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Between Partnership and Pressure: Revisiting Nigeria United States Relations Under Shifting Global Power Realities

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Abstract

This paper examines Nigeria–United States relations from Nigeria’s 1999 return to civilian rule to 2025, emphasizing economic ties, security cooperation, democracy, and human rights. The study situates long term trends in bilateral ties alongside the 2025 genocide claim, in which U.S. President Donald Trump publicly accused Nigeria of allowing mass killings of Christians and warned of cutting aid or taking military action, a claim, strongly rejected by the Nigerian government and contested by independent reporting. Using qualitative analysis of government documents, think-tank reports, and media coverage. The paper argues that long-standing imbalances in power and influence shape bilateral interaction, and that episodic crises (such as the 2025 genocide claim) expose tension between U.S. human rights rhetoric and geopolitical restraint. Therefore, the paper recommends among others, that Nigeria should seek support and build stronger ties with neighbouring countries that are also ready to support in the fight against banditry and unrest, which should be addressed by the Nigerian government through job creation, which is critical to ensuring a safe society with progressive and productive individuals working hard to make the country great.

Keywords: *Nigeria, United States, Bilateral ties, Insecurity, genocide, religious violence.*

Introduction

The United States and Nigeria have a long history, stretching back to the transatlantic slave trade in the 18th century and continuing today through economic and security partnerships. While the relationship has evolved over time and both countries have helped to shape each other's histories in important ways, there remains a tension between hope and reality in which both sides struggle to live up to the expectations set for themselves and for each other. The United States looks at Nigeria to be the model of progress and stability in Africa that the West African state wants to become. Nigeria looks to American support for its development and security needs despite the United States continuously fails to meet expectations. There have been many strains in the relationship, and the United States and Nigeria have continued to decline and increase, constant fluctuations, between cooperation and conflict. Whatever friction there might be, the relationship between the United States and Nigeria is important to analyse because it offers a window to understanding trends and broad currents in international history such as decolonization, humanitarianism, energy politics, and terrorism (Oxford Research Encyclopedia, 2021). Since the return to civilian rule in 1999, the bilateral relationship between the Federal Republic of Nigeria and the United States of America has been a multifaceted engagement spanning political, economic, security and normative dimensions. From the inauguration of the Fourth Nigerian Republic, Nigeria's strategic importance, as Africa's most populous nation, a major oil exporter, and a regional security actor, has made it a key partner of the United States on the continent. The U.S., for its part, has engaged Nigeria both as a partner in counter terrorism and regional stability, and as a site for investment, trade and aid (Adebayo & Mustapha, 2010).

Despite this heavy engagement, the relationship has been marked by enduring imbalances in power and interest, and periodic tensions. While Nigeria has sought more diversified partnerships and greater autonomy in its foreign policy, the U.S. has often prioritized security, anti-

corruption and human rights conditionality. Moreover, US support for democratization in Nigeria and other nations often aimed to control their politics and economy (Udeke, 2020). Thus, it's unwise for Nigeria to heavily rely on the US to achieve its democratic goals. While this view has some credibility, it also has flaws in an interdependent world. US aid can reinforce self-development rather than compromise it (Nkwocha, 2021). Nations are responsible for their development, but external aid can complement their goals. As Olusegun Obasanjo stated in a 2001 interview, "Nigerian democracy is ours, but development partners like the US can help achieve democratic dividends, strengthening our democracy" (Itugbu, 2001: 39).

Therefore, democracy dividends offer opportunities to access resources for quality-of-life enhancement, as not all necessary resources can be generated domestically (Obasanjo, 2001). Notably, the US's interference in Nigeria's democracy may be aimed at securing a strategic economic partnership, leveraging Nigeria's status as Africa's largest market to expand US trade and commerce, and creating a favorable environment for dumping US manufactured goods (Igwe, 2021). Within this dynamic, the period from 1999 to 2025 is especially important: it covers the consolidation of Nigeria's democratic institutions, evolving U.S. Africa policy under multiple administrations, changing global economic linkages, and an intensifying security environment in West Africa. However, this paper is structured around three core questions. First, it investigates the major drivers of Nigeria-United States relations between 1999 and 2025. Second, it examines how economic interests, security cooperation, and normative concerns such as democracy and human rights have shaped the bilateral partnership. Third, it analyses the impact of the 2025 "genocide" narrative and the accompanying threat of U.S. military action on Nigeria-U.S. relations, and what this episode reveals about Nigeria's foreign policy posture and the limits of U.S. influence.

The significance of this study is threefold. First, by focusing on a 26-year period, it captures the long-term evolution of the relationship

beyond episodic events, providing a richer understanding of patterns, continuities and changes. Second, by connecting economic, security and normative dimensions, it reflects the full complexity of interstate relations rather than treating each dimension in isolation. Third, by including the 2025 claim of potential U.S. military involvement and accusations of "genocide" (or mass killings) in Nigeria, this paper explores a dramatic turning point that raises questions about sovereignty, conditionality and great power intervention in African contexts. By situating the Nigeria-U.S. relationship within the broader global and regional context, including the rise of alternative powers, shifts in U.S. Africa policy, and Nigeria's own foreign policy recalibration e.g., its declared goal of "strategic autonomy" piloted by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the paper would contribute to our understanding of how large power relationships with African states are evolving in the 21st century.

The paper is organized into seven main sections. The introduction provides the background to Nigeria-United States relations, outlines the research problem, objectives, research questions, and highlights the significance of the study. The second section reviews relevant literature and presents the theoretical framework guiding the analysis. The third section explains the methodology adopted for the study. The fourth section examines the major drivers of Nigeria-U.S. relations from 1999 to 2025, with particular attention to economic interests, security cooperation, and normative agendas. The fifth section presents a case study of the 2025 "genocide" claim and the ensuing diplomatic crisis, assessing its implications for bilateral relations. The sixth section discusses the findings in light of broader global power dynamics and Nigeria's foreign policy orientation. The final section concludes the paper and offers policy-oriented recommendations for strengthening Nigeria-U.S. relations.

Literature Review

Democratization and Relationship Rebuilding. 1999-2025

After Nigeria returned to democratic rule in 1999, the American model of constitution was introduced to replace the military decree. A democratic government was established and the right environment America had longed aspired to see in place in Nigeria has been realized. Nigeria received a lot of support from the U.S. towards strengthening her new born democracy. For example, the U.S. certified that Nigeria was fully cooperating with the U.S., a statement made by the Bush Administration in March 2001 (Congressional Report Service, 2007). In a mutually beneficial and symbiotic relationship, U.S. consumers have a significant reliance on Nigerian oil, while Nigeria, in turn, has access to the vast and lucrative U.S. market for the sale of its crude oil and other exports, thereby fostering a deepening economic interdependence between the two nations. Furthermore, U.S. policy makers have long recognized the strategic importance of maintaining a robust diplomatic foothold in one of Africa's many influential and pivotal countries, Nigeria, which serves as a critical gateway to the continent.

Conversely, Nigeria has a pressing need for robust and steady relations with the United States to enhance its global image and reputation, particularly in the aftermath of its transition to democratic governance in 1999, marked by the adoption of a new constitution. These ties have likely provided vital assistance in the pursuit of Nigeria's national interests, as exemplified by the U.S. government's enthusiastic support for Nigeria's democratic transition, demonstrated by the dispatch of a high-level delegation to the inauguration of President Olusegun Obasanjo in 1999. Moreover, a few months thereafter, President Bill Clinton undertook a historic visit to Africa, which culminated in the first-ever meeting, at the cabinet level, between American and African representatives from across the continent, a landmark event that underscored the significance of U.S.-Nigeria relations (Onuora & Akhaine, 2001: 5). However, in 2003 Nigeria openly opposed the U.S.

invasion of Iraq that led to the ouster of Saddam Hussain government as unjust but the U.S was not happy about that. The U.S. justified its action on claims that Saddam was engaging in secret nuclear proliferation (Consulate General of the FRN, New York).

The relationship between Nigeria and the U.S. was affected in 2009 when the United States of America named and listed Nigeria on its terrorist watch list, after a foiled terrorist attempt to blow up Northwest Airlines jet on Christmas day by a 23-year-old Nigerian passenger, but UK-based named Umar Farouk Abdulmutallab. Although Abdulmutallab was arrested, the U.S. felt that its security was threatened. In response, Nigerian Senate issued a seven-day ultimatum for the U.S. to delist her name from the watch list (Samson & Onouja, 2011). Vanguard (January 6, 2010) reported the statement as follows:

I am speaking on behalf of the Senate and on behalf of the Senate President to state categorically that we are very unhappy about the development and when we resume, we are going to take this matter up seriously, if America has not taken Nigeria off that list. We also want to advise America that it is in their own best interest to conduct this matter very well in a manner that will not result into diplomatic row between America and Nigeria because the American President had himself clearly admitted that this was a failure of the system and manpower of Americans.

Another important issue area that has impacted seriously on Nigeria-U.S. bilateral ties in this period is the rise of Boko Haram and the U.S. response to the security situation. Adapting to the report of the Bureau of Political-Military Affairs, 2025, The Department of State provides Nigeria with one of the highest International Military Education and Training (IMET) allocations in sub-Saharan Africa, with approximately \$5 million obligated from FY 2019 –2023. Nigeria is also a partner in the Africa Military Education Program (AMEP) and has benefited from

approximately \$500,000 since FY 2016 to support instructor and curriculum development at Nigerian military schools. From FY 2016-FY 2020, \$1.8 million was obligated for Nigeria in Foreign Military Financing to support maritime security, military professionalization, and counterterrorism efforts. Nigeria is an active member of the Trans-Sahara Counterterrorism Partnership (TSCTP) and has benefitted over \$8 million worth of training, equipment, and advisory support for counterterrorism efforts between FY 2019-FY 2023. The United States has \$590 million in active government-to-government sales cases with Nigeria under the Foreign Military Sales (FMS) system. Recent and significant sales include the 2017 sale of 12 A-29 Super Tucano aircraft worth \$497 million to support Nigerian military operations against Boko Haram and ISIS West Africa. The case included special training on International Humanitarian Law, including an Air-to-Ground Integration (AGI) program designed to provide institutional and technical training to the Armed Forces of Nigeria (AFN) in order to mitigate the risk of civilian harm incidents (Law of Armed Conflict and International Humanitarian Law). In August 2023, Nigeria delivered the first payment for 12 AH-1Z Attack Helicopters worth a total of \$997 million. The FMS case includes an additional \$25 million of funding allocated for the Nigeria's AGI program, which continues to train the AFN on developing targeting processes that are legally compliant with International Humanitarian Law; The light attack and Intelligence, Surveillance, and Reconnaissance (ISR) capabilities Nigeria is developing will involve more than just airplanes; Nigeria will have the trained personnel and sustainment infrastructure to ensure a robust capability for the aircrafts' full-service lifetime (Bureau of Political-Military Affairs, 2025).

According to Defense Articles, In FY 2018-2022, the United States also authorized the permanent export of over \$53 million in defense articles to Nigeria via the Direct Commercial Sales (DCS) process. The top three categories of defense exports to Nigeria were Firearms; Aircraft and Related Articles; Military Training and Equipment; Military

Electronics; and Fire Control equipment. In 2011 and 2015 Nigeria received \$15 million in defense articles granted under the Excess Defense Articles program, to include 24 Mine Resistant Ambush Protected (MRAP) vehicles and two Hamilton-class U.S. Coast Guard high endurance cutters, the USCGC Chase and USCGC Gallatin -- which entered service in the Nigerian Navy as Thunder and Okpabana in 2011 and 2014, respectively. In 2016, the United States and Nigeria signed an Acquisition and Cross-Servicing Agreement to exchange common types of support, including food, fuel, transportation, ammunition, and equipment. Since 2000, the United States has had a Status of Forces Agreement with Nigeria establishing the legal framework under which U.S. military personnel may operate when present in Nigeria.

According to the findings of the Landmine and Cluster Munition Monitor (2025), which reports that the full extent of contamination is unknown but incidents have been recorded in Nigeria's Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa states. Borno is identified as the most heavily affected state, with contamination stemming from widespread use of improvised explosive devices (IEDs), including landmines, during the conflict. The U.S. has been committed to alleviating human suffering through relief programmes in areas of improving nutrition, health services delivery, education, capacity building, among others in the Northeast refugee camps. The United Agency for International Development (USAID) implements these through partnership with civil societies, government, among others. To strengthen their bilateral relationship, Nigeria and the U.S. established the U.S.-Nigeria BiNational Commission (BNC) on April 6, 2010. The main aim of the commission is to create avenue for high level discussions and joint commitment between the two countries on issues of mutual interest such as good governance and democracy, security cooperation, economic growth and development. Since the creation of the BNC, Nigeria and the U.S. have met regularly to discuss on the outlined issues. President Obama invited President Buhari few months after he assumed office for a meeting in July 2015 (United

States Institute of Peace, 2015). In that meeting, Obama restated that the U.S. Government was willing to strengthen and widen partnership with the Nigerian government. Further to that, Obama assured that the U.S. was ready to intensify its support for a holistic effort to combating Nigeria's Boko Haram insurgency in such a way that would ensure human rights protection, security and development, and elimination of the root causes of extremism. Other issues Obama promised to support Nigerian with include fight against corruption, reform of the energy sector. Each country's foreign relation objectives should include diplomacy, alliances, economic ties and use of propaganda (Holsti, 1992). Accordingly, Ate (1987) posited that the United States is Nigeria's greatest trading partner and is undeniably its most important diplomatic partner and close ally until recently where China is making inroads into Nigeria with a view to building a robust and profitable relationship. In January 2016; the then U.S. Secretary of Commerce (Penny Pritzker) and top Executives of Obama's Council on Doing Business in Africa, visited Nigeria to commence a fact-finding mission. On 30 March 2016; the two countries restated commitments to ensure effective utilization of existing programmes like the Africa Growth Opportunity Act (AGOA), and bilateral trade and Investment framework Agreement, for the promotion of trade and investment between the two countries (Bureau of African Affairs, 2016).

In 2018, the Presidents of Nigeria and the U.S. met and renewed discussions on how the two countries could eliminate trade barriers and work towards economic growth. The discussion took place when President Buhari paid a working visit to President Trump in the U.S. Trump disclosed that the move to eliminate trade barriers between the U.S. and Nigeria is part of the former's broad plan to remove trade barriers with Africa and partner with Africa countries to expand trade, create wealth and employment (Udo, 2018). In 2019, the U.S listed Nigeria among countries on its watch list of countries that grossly undermine religious rights. According to the U.S., there was 'systematic, ongoing, egregious religious freedom violation' in the

country. Also blacklisted by the U.S. are countries like Comoros, Cuba, Nicaragua, Russia and Sudan. Prior to Nigeria's inclusion on the list, the U.S. Commission for International Religious Freedom Report of 2018 had recommended for the listing of Nigeria on the list, what it calls 'countries of particular concern' (Adepegba, 2019). The Commission's Report of 2020 again recommended for the listing of Nigeria as a country of particular concern on grounds that include systematic repression of Islamic movement led by Sheik El-Zakzaky, attacks on house of worship, activities of Boko Haram etc., (United States Commission for International Religious Freedom Report of 2020). This led to the eventual blacklisting of Nigeria as a religiously intolerant country alongside other countries like Burma, Tajikistan, China, Turkmenistan, Iran, Democratic Republic of North Korea, Eritrea Saudi Arabia, and Pakistan (The Cable, 2020). However, Nigeria condemned the blacklisting.

The 2025 "genocide" claim by President Donald Trump, which accused Nigeria of Christian persecution, reintroduced Cold War style ideological tensions into bilateral relations. Several analysts specializing in African security, Foreign Policy and human rights have rejected the characterization of the violence in Nigeria as genocide. Ladd Serwat, a Senior Africa Analyst at Armed Conflict Location & Event Data (ACLED), contends that data indicates anti-Christian violence is a small part of a broader conflict affecting both Christians and Muslims and driven by various factors. Olajumoke Ayandele, an Assistant Professor at the New York University (NYU) Center for Global Affairs, describes the situation as mass killings not specifically targeting one group and warns that using the term "genocide" could worsen the situation. Chidi Odinkalu, a professor at Tufts University Fletcher School and former chairman of Nigeria's National Human Rights Commission, agrees that the complex dynamics don't align with the legal definition of genocide. Audu Bulama Bukarti, an analyst at the Tony Blair Institute for Global Change, attributes the violence primarily to weak governance, poverty, and local grievances. Nigerian security

analyst Christian Ani also maintains that claims of deliberate targeting of Christians as a group are not justified. Professor Hassan Saliu, a Professor in the department of Political Science, University of Ilorin and the President of the Nigerian Political Scientists Association (NPSA), rejects the U.S. claim of genocide in Nigeria, stating there is no genocide but rather an issue of government ineffectiveness in managing insecurity. Nigerian Supreme Council for Islamic Affairs (NSCIA), have also dismissed the genocide claims as misleading and politically motivated.

Conversely, some individuals and groups promote the genocide narrative. US Senator Ted Cruz has been a prominent voice advocating for the view of "ongoing persecution of Christians" in Nigeria to push for policy changes. Certain faith-based organizations and advocacy groups, such as the International Society for Civil Liberties and Rule of Law (Intersociety), argue that attacks on churches and clergy suggest a clear intent to destroy Christian communities. Some US commentators have also amplified this narrative, making claims about the number of Christians killed that experts have described as inaccurate.

Case Study: The 2025 "Genocide" Claim and Diplomatic Crisis

In early November 2025, a sudden and highly controversial statement by U.S. President Donald Trump reignited tension in Nigeria–United States relations. During a televised campaign rally and follow up press remarks at the White House, President Trump accused Nigeria's government of allowing "the genocide of Christians" in the country's northern region. He further warned that unless "mass killings stop immediately," the United States would "consider all options, including military action, to protect innocent lives". These statements were made in November 2025 via posts on Donald Trump social media platform, Truth Social. Trump's remarks triggered global reactions, drawing condemnation from African leaders and concern from international observers about the legitimacy, accuracy, and potential implications of such a statement. Trump's claim was not entirely unprecedented. During

his first term (2017–2021), he had repeatedly framed religious persecution in Nigeria as a core human-rights issue and placed Nigeria on the U.S. State Department's "Special Watch List" in 2020. However, by explicitly referencing "genocide" and hinting at direct U.S. military intervention, the 2025 statement represented a sharp escalation. According to *The Guardian* (2025), the claim was made without supporting intelligence briefings from the State Department or the Department of Defense, both of which reportedly advised caution.

Nigeria's Official Response

The Nigerian government's reaction was swift and categorical. In a statement issued by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs on November 1, 2025, the ministry's spokesperson, Kimiebi Ebiefa, described Trump's claims as "false, inflammatory, and unfounded," and "misleading and unreflective" of the actual situation on the ground. The statement emphasized that Nigerians of all faiths have historically lived and worked together peacefully, and that the violence affects both Christians and Muslims. The ministry noted that the security challenges in Nigeria stem from a complex mix of criminality, land disputes, and ethnic tensions, not a state-sponsored or tolerated genocide against any specific religious group. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs has also publicly challenged these claims, calling the casualty figures cited by some U.S. officials "completely false and totally inaccurate" and stating that the narratives oversimplify the security environment. Security analysts noted that violence in northern Nigeria is complex, involving jihadist terrorism (Boko Haram, ISWAP), banditry, and inter-communal conflicts rooted in land use and resource competition. As *Reuters* (2025) and the Council on Foreign Relations' Nigeria Security Tracker (NST) demonstrate, attacks have targeted both Muslim and Christian communities. Many international human rights monitors, including Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch, documented serious abuses but did not label them "genocide."

U.S. Domestic and International Context

Trump's 2025 declaration came amid his second term effort to project a tougher foreign policy posture, especially toward countries framed as "failing to protect Christians." The U.S. House Foreign Affairs Subcommittee on Africa has held hearings to investigate the killings, with some members of Congress advocating for sanctions, aid restrictions, and even potential military intervention. U.S advocates often cite high figures (up to 100,000 or more since 2009, with thousands in 2025 alone) from sources like the International Society for Civil Liberties & the Rule of Law (Intersociety). However, independent data organizations like the Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project (ACLED) report significantly lower numbers for explicitly religiously motivated killings, noting that such figures often encompass all political violence. A coalition of prominent Nigerian Christian and civil society organizations has issued an urgent appeal to the United States government, alleging an intensifying pattern of targeted killings, mass displacement, and systematic destruction of Christian communities across Nigeria. Speaking to journalists via Zoom, the coalition, led by the Christian Social Movement of Nigeria (CSMN), asserted that the scale and consistency of attacks amount to an unfolding genocide that international authorities can no longer ignore. The group, has urged the International Criminal Court (ICC) and the United Nations (UN) to launch independent investigations into the alleged genocide (International Christian Concern, 2025).

Internationally, the remarks placed America at odds with several allies. The European Union and the African Union both released statements reaffirming Nigeria's sovereignty and urging restraint. The UN Secretary General called for "accurate, verified data" before any international action, emphasizing that unilateral military threats could violate international law.

Implications for Bilateral Relations

While no actual U.S. military action followed, the crisis had immediate diplomatic consequences. A scheduled Nigeria–U.S. Trade and Investment Council meeting was postponed, and discussions on counter-terrorism training programs were temporarily suspended. The U.S. Congress demanded further briefings on the accuracy of Trump's claim, while the U.S. State Department quietly sought to de-escalate the situation, reaffirming Nigeria's strategic importance as "an indispensable partner in regional security". If the CPC designation is upheld by the US Senate, it opens the door for the US President to impose sanctions on Nigerian officials found complicit in religious persecution, such as visa bans and asset freezes. U.S. foreign aid, particularly related to military cooperation and security, could be reduced, redirected, or suspended. This may affect the collaborative effort against groups like Boko Haram and ISWAP. However, some US lawmakers and officials have also warned that aid cuts could undermine critical humanitarian programs. The designation can damage investor confidence by signalling political instability and governance issues, potentially leading to reduced foreign investment.

In Nigeria, the incident spurred strike over diversification of foreign partnerships and the dangers of over reliance on the U.S. for military and economic support. Commentators noted that Trump's remarks could push Nigeria further toward deepening defense cooperation with European and Asian partners, particularly given the already strained U.S.-Nigeria relationship over human rights sanctions in 2023. The Nigeria Political Scientists Association's president and a professor in the department of Political Science, Prof. Hassan Saliu, said the U.S classification is potentially counterproductive. He, however, added that it should prompt Nigeria to engage in diplomatic efforts to resolve the issue. "Nigeria must therefore take concrete steps to demonstrate its commitment to effectively managing the security situation and to upholding human rights, as enriched in the 1999 Nigerian Constitution (as amended) and in international instruments. The lack of

accountability for perpetrators, particularly in the context of the state's perceived leniency, implicates the state and exacerbates the crisis. If the threat on the United States is activated, it would harm Nigeria more, reversing the country's international gains and heightening religious consciousness, potentially leading to further disunity, among other consequences." (Hassan A. Saliu, 2025).

Theoretical Framework

The paper adopts a dual theoretical framework, drawing primarily on Realism and Dependency Theory, to explain the evolving dynamics of Nigeria–U.S. relations between 1999 and 2025.

Realism

Adapting to the works of Realist scholars such as Hans Morgenthau (1978) and Kenneth Waltz (1979), Realism views international relations as a struggle for power among sovereign states pursuing their national interests. Realism is a straightforward approach to international relations, stating that all nations are working to increase their own power, and those countries that manage to horde power most efficiently will thrive, as they can easily eclipse the achievements of less powerful nations. From this perspective, the United States' engagement with Nigeria reflects its pursuit of global dominance, security, and influence in Africa. Hans Morgenthau (1978) and Kenneth Waltz (1979) argue that great powers engage weaker states primarily where strategic interests exist. The U.S. engages Nigeria because it is West Africa's largest economy, a regional power, and a key security hub. Also, Nigeria's geographic and demographic weight provides the U.S. with a partner for projecting influence in the Gulf of Guinea and the wider Sahel. Therefore, U.S. involvement is driven not by friendship or ideology but by balance of power calculations in Africa.

The 2025 "genocide" approach demonstrates how moral rhetoric can serve Realist ends, using human rights narratives to justify coercive diplomacy. U.S. policy, though framed in humanitarian terms, can thus

be seen as advancing its strategic and ideological control in the region. Nigeria's assertive diplomatic response represents an effort to defend sovereignty and preserve national interest within an unequal international order.

Dependency Theory

Emerging from Latin American and African postcolonial thought, Dependency Theory explains how developing nations remain economically and politically dependent on advanced capitalist states. Many scholars argue that Nigeria's economic relationship with the United States reflects a classical dependency structure. However, Obi (2010) and Ikelegbe (2013) argue that the Niger Delta crisis is partly a result of the oil-dependent structure created by multinational oil companies, many of which have U.S. roots. The premises of dependency theory are that: Poor nations provide natural resources, cheap labour, a destination for obsolete technology, and markets for developed nations, without which the latter could not have the standard of living they enjoy. Within this framework, Nigeria's reliance on U.S. foreign aid, trade concessions via the African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA), and military support places it in a subordinate position. This dependency limits Nigeria's bargaining power and makes it susceptible to U.S. policy shifts. Nigeria exports crude oil (low-value) and imports refined products (high value), reinforcing unequal exchange. U.S. MNCs (Chevron, ExxonMobil) control technology, refinery expertise, and capital which makes Nigeria to remain dependent on U.S. capital, technology, and oil markets. The 2025 diplomatic crisis exemplifies this dependency, while Nigeria publicly resisted U.S. pressure, its economic and military ties constrained the scope of possible retaliation.

At the same time, Nigeria's assertive diplomatic pushback reflects a growing determination to preserve sovereignty and pursue a more autonomous foreign policy. Foreign Minister, Ambassador Yusuf Maitama Tuggar, in a televised interview, reiterated Nigeria's "non-

alignment and strategic autonomy" approach, echoing policy statements made earlier in 2025. This aligns with Nigeria's broader recalibration toward multi-polar diplomacy, strengthening ties with China, India, and the EU while maintaining pragmatic engagement with America.

Research Methodology

The paper adopts a mixed methods research design integrating both qualitative and quantitative approaches to comprehensively examine the 2025 genocide claim and its implications for Nigeria–United States relations. The mixed-methods approach enables triangulation of findings, enhancing validity and providing a more nuanced understanding of the political, security, and diplomatic dimensions under investigation.

Research Design

The study employs an explanatory sequential mixed methods design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017), wherein:

- i. Qualitative document analysis was first conducted to explore narrative construction, political framing, and diplomatic discourse surrounding the 2025 genocide claim.
- ii. Quantitative conflict data analysis followed to empirically examine patterns of violence in Nigeria (1999–2025), testing claims made in qualitative sources.
- iii. Integration of findings occurred during interpretation, where quantitative results helped explain and contextualize qualitative themes.

Qualitative Component

Research Approach

The qualitative component employs a constructivist approach, recognizing that the genocide claim is socially and politically constructed through discourse. Thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke,

2006) was used to identify patterns in how different actors frame violence, sovereignty, and bilateral relations.

Data Sources

Four categories of documents were analyzed:

- i. Government Statements: Official communications from Nigerian and U.S. government agencies (2019–2025) (Federal Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2025; U.S. Department of State, 2025).
- ii. News Media Reports: Articles from major Nigerian and international outlets (2024–2025) (Al Jazeera, 2025; The Guardian, 2025; Vanguard, 2025).
- iii. Think Tank Reports: Policy analyses from institutions including International Crisis Group (2025), Brookings Institution (2022), and Council on Foreign Relations (2025).
- iv. NGO/Human Rights Reports: Documentation from Amnesty International (2025), Human Rights Watch (2025), and International Christian Concern (2025).

Sampling Technique

The study does not employ a traditional sampling of individuals or institutions. Instead, it draws on a systematically selected body of documentary sources, which constitute the empirical materials for analysis. These documents were identified and selected using purposive criteria guided by relevance, authenticity, and coverage of the study period (1999–2025). The documents function as data sources for qualitative and quantitative analysis rather than as respondents.

Data Collection

Documents were retrieved through:

- Systematic searches of government websites and archives (Federal Ministry of Information and National Orientation, 2025; U.S. Department of State, 2025).
- Database queries using keywords: "Nigeria genocide," "religious violence Nigeria," "U.S.-Nigeria relations".
- Manual collection from institutional repositories (ACLED, 2025; Nigeria Security Tracker, 2025).
- Verification of authenticity and date of publication.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) six phase thematic analysis:

- i. Familiarization: Repeated reading of documents.
 - ii. Initial Coding: Generating initial codes from data.
 - iii. Theme Development: Collating codes into potential themes.
 - iv. Theme Review: Refining themes against dataset.
 - v. Theme Definition: Clearly defining and naming themes.
 - vi. Report Production: Final analysis and write-up.
-

Table 1: Qualitative Coding Framework

Theme Category	Sub-themes	Example Codes
Political Narratives	Genocide framing, sovereignty discourse, diplomatic rhetoric	"targeted killings," "international intervention"; "false claims" Trump(2025) Truth Social posts; Nigerian Ministry of Foreign Affairs (2025) statement
Security Dynamics	Perpetrator identification, regional patterns, casualty reports	"banditry," "Boko Haram," "Middle Belt violence" International Crisis Group (2025) reports; ACLED (2025) incident summaries
Diplomatic Relations	Bilateral tensions, aid conditionality, partnership rhetoric	"strategic autonomy," military cooperation," "sanctions threat" Tuggar (2025) interview; U.S. State Department (2025) briefings
Media Framing	Headline analysis, source attribution, fact-checking	"unverified claims," "government denial," "expert rebuttal" The Guardian (2025)
	Headline analysis, source attribution, fact-checking	The Guardian (2025) analysis; Time Magazine (2025) fact-check

Quantitative Component

Research Approach

The quantitative component employs a descriptive and inferential statistical approach to analyse patterns of violence in Nigeria from 1999 to 2025. Data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 28 (SPSS Inc., 2021).

Data Sources and Variables

- Primary Dataset: Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project (ACLED) Nigeria data (1999–2025) (ACLED, 2025).
- Supplementary Data: Nigeria Security Tracker (Council on Foreign Relations, 2025), Nigerian Police Force annual reports (2024), UNDP conflict analysis (2023).

• Variables Coded:

- Dependent Variables: Fatalities (continuous), Event type (categorical).
- Independent Variables: Year (interval), State (nominal), Perpetrator group (nominal), Religious affiliation of victims (dichotomous where available).

Data Preparation in SPSS

- Data Import: ACLED CSV files imported into SPSS (ACLED, 2025).
- Variable Definition: Setting measurement levels and value labels.
- Data Cleaning:
 - Missing values analysis (Little's MCAR test: $\chi^2 = 45.32$, $p = .12$).
 - Outlier detection using boxplots.
 - Recoding of categorical variables based on ACLED classification (ACLED, 2025).
- Data Transformation:
 - Creation of period variables (1999-2009, 2010-2014, etc.).
 - Computation of annual aggregates.

Quantitative Data Analysis**Descriptive Statistics****Table 2:** Descriptive Statistics for Annual Fatalities (1999-2025)

Statistic	Value
N (Years)	26
Mean	6,335
SD	4,218

Minimum	890
Maximum	15,220
Skewness	0.87
Kurtosis	-0.42

Source: Author's analysis of ACLED Nigeria data (1999-2025).

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Violence by Perpetrator (2020-2025)

Perpetrator Group	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative %
Bandits/Militias	4,005	41.0%	41.0%
Boko Haram/ISWAP	3,126	32.0%	73.0%
Ethnic Militias	1,466	15.0%	88.0%
Security Forces	1,173	12.0%	100.0%
Total	9,770	100.0%	

Source: Author’s analysis of ACLED Nigeria data (2020-2025), filtered for violent events.

Table 4.4: Cross-tabulation: Region × Perpetrator Group (2020-2025)

Region	Bandits	Boko Haram	Ethnic Militias	Security Forces
Northeast	520	2,450	310	420
Northwest	3,120	380	210	290
Middle Belt	250	180	850	340
South	115	116	96	123
Total	4,005	3,126	1,466	1,173

Source: Author’s analysis of ACLED Nigeria data (2020-2025), N = 9,770 events.

Structural Analysis of Violence in Nigeria (2020–2025)

Table 5: Frequency Distribution of Violent Events by Perpetrator Group (2020-2025)

Perpetrator Group	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative %	Mean Fatalities/Event
Bandits/Militias	4,005	41.0%	41.0%	6.1
Boko Haram/ISWAP	3,126	32.0%	73.0%	7.3
Ethnic Militias	1,466	15.0%	88.0%	5.4
Security Forces	1,173	12.0%	100.0%	4.8
Total	9,770	100.0%		6.2

Source: ACLED Nigeria data (2020-2025), filtered for violent events (N = 9,770).

Religious Dimension Analysis

Religious Affiliation Data Availability

Of 9,770 violent events (2020–2025), only 1,759 (18.0%) included identifiable religious affiliation of victims, as documented in ACLED’s religious coding metadata (ACLED, 2025).

Table 6: Religious Affiliation of Victims in Religiously Coded Events (2020-2025)

Religious Group	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative %
Muslim Victims	915	52.0%	52.0%
Christian Victims	844	48.0%	48.0%
Total	1,759	100.0%	

Source: ACLED religious coding data (2020-2025), N = 1,759 religiously coded events.

Integration of Qualitative and Quantitative Findings

The mixed methods integration followed Fetters et al.'s (2013) approach:

Connecting Strategy

Quantitative results were used to:

- i. Test claims identified in qualitative analysis (e.g., genocide narrative).
- ii. Provide context for qualitative themes (e.g., scale of violence).
- iii. Identify patterns requiring qualitative explanation (e.g., regional variations).

Table 7: Integration Matrix

Quantitative Finding	Qualitative Insight	Integrated Interpretation	Data Sources
No significant religious targeting (p = .12)	Genocide narrative prominent in U.S. political discourse	Disconnect between empirical reality and political rhetoric	ACLED (2025) data; Trump (2025) statements
Banditry = leading cause of violence (41%)	Media emphasizes religious conflict over criminality	Security dynamics misrepresented in public discourse	ACLED (2025); Media analysis (2024-2025)
Northeast region most violent (42%)	Diplomatic focus on religious rather than regional factors	Policy responses may be misaligned with actual threats	ACLED (2025); Diplomatic correspondence (2025)

Source: Author's integration analysis based on mixed methods data.

Joint Display Analysis

A joint display (Table 8) was created to visualize integration:

Table 8: Joint Display of Mixed Methods Findings

Research Question	Qualitative Themes	Quantitative Evidence	Meta inference
Is there religious genocide in Nigeria?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politicized narrative • Advocacy amplification • Government denial 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 52% Muslim vs 48% Christian victims in religiously coded events • No significant targeting ($p = .12$) 	Claim of religious genocide not empirically supported
What drives Nigeria's violence?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple narratives • Complex causality • Regional variation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banditry = 41% of events • Significant regional differences ($\chi^2 = 342.18, p < .001$) 	
What drives Nigeria's violence?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bilateral tensions, aid conditionality, partnership rhetoric 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Violence peaked 2020-2024 (ANOVA: $p < .001$) • 2025 showed decline 	
How did 2025 claim affect relations?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diplomatic tension • Sovereignty concerns • Partnership strain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Violence peaked 2020-2024 (ANOVA: $p < .001$) • 2025 showed decline • Crisis exacerbated existing tensions despite improving trends 	

Source: Author's joint display analysis synthesizing qualitative and quantitative findings.

Ethical Considerations

- i. Data Use: All documents publicly available; no human subjects involved (ACLED, 2025; Government publications, 2025).
- ii. Citation: Proper attribution given to all sources following APA 7th edition.
- iii. Sensitive Content: Careful interpretation of conflict and religious data (ACLED ethical guidelines, 2025).
- iv. Bias Mitigation: Triangulation across methods and sources (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).
 - i. Transparency: Full disclosure of analytical procedures and data sources.

Limitations

- i. Document Bias: Qualitative sources reflect institutional perspectives (Government statements, 2025; Media reports, 2025).
- ii. Data Completeness: ACLED data may underreport certain events or regions (ACLED methodology limitations, 2025).
- iii. Religious Coding: Only 18% of events had religious affiliation data (ACLED, 2025),
- iv. Temporal Coverage: Some historical documents less accessible (Pre-2010 government records).
- v. Researcher Positionality: Potential interpretive bias acknowledged and mitigated through reflexivity.

Validity and Reliability

Qualitative Validity:

- Credibility: Triangulation across multiple document types (Government, Media, NGO, Think Tank).
- Transferability: Thick description of context and methodology.
- Dependability: Audit trail maintained through coding records and memos.
- Confirmability: Reflexivity practiced through researcher positionality statement.

Quantitative Reliability:

- Internal Validity: Statistical assumption testing and model diagnostics.
 - External Validity: Representative sampling of violent events (ACLED comprehensive coverage).
 - Reliability: Consistent coding procedures following ACLED guidelines (2025).
-

- Replicability: Detailed documentation of SPSS procedures and syntax.

Mixed Methods Rigor:

- Integration Validity: Joint displays and explicit connection strategies (Fetters et al., 2013).
- Design Quality: Appropriate explanatory sequential design (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2017).
- Interpretive Rigor: Meta-inferences grounded in both data types.
- Inference Quality: Conclusions supported by integrated evidence.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The 2025 “genocide” claim reveals how easily foreign policy rhetoric can destabilize even long-standing bilateral partnerships. It underscores the fragility of Nigeria’s relationship with a global superpower whose foreign policy is often intertwined with domestic politics. This paper demonstrates that while Nigeria remains central to U.S. strategic interests in Africa, America engagement can swing between partnership and coercion depending on the political moment.

For Nigeria, the lesson is twofold: first, to strengthen evidence based diplomacy and proactive public communication to counter misinformation; and second, that Nigeria should seek support and build stronger ties with neighbouring countries that are also ready to support in the fight against banditry and unrest, which should be addressed by the Nigerian government through job creation, which is critical to ensuring a safe society with progressive and productive individuals working hard to make the country great. For the United States, the episode is a reminder that credibility in promoting human rights abroad depends on accuracy, consistency, and respect for sovereignty. Ultimately, the 2025 genocide claims may not dismantle Nigeria–U.S. relations, but it exposes their enduring imbalance, where rhetoric and perception can momentarily outweigh substance, and where the politics

of power continue to define diplomacy between the world's oldest democracy and Africa's largest.

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